

Rigorous Computational Jyotisa

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Abstract

In this note the author investigates how a collection of gravitational waves impacts a tract of three axons. By extension and in principle, this can yield the impact of Zodiacal stellar positions on the brain of an individual, assuming the “houses” each have a distinct gravitational wave source.

Consider a tract of three ephaptically coupled axons. Previous work by the author and collaborators has addressed the conduction of action potentials on the three axons in the presence of a single gravitational wave source. In this note, we present simulations of the impact of eight simultaneously radiating gravitational wave sources. One can interpret these results as speaking of the impact of the Zodiacal “houses” of astrology or *jyotisa* on a specific individual. By encoding the eight sources in a single source expression, we are able to use the old program for this new purpose. Figure 1 shows axon 1, Figure 2 shows axon 2, and Figure 3 shows axon 3 in all the three conditions: without (or very weak) gravitational sources, with eight sources and with eight other sources. The strain is artificially high to show the impact. All the sources have the same strain but differing frequencies for the gravitational waves. In future work we aim to link this result to brain quantum computation and behavior, possibly opening up *jyotisa* to mathematical rigor in its predictions.

No Gravitational Radiation

Eight Sources

Eight Different Sources

Figure 1: Axon 1 in three conditions.

No Gravitational Radiation

Eight Sources

Eight Different Sources

Figure 2: Axon 2 in three conditions.

No Gravitational Radiation

Eight Sources

Eight Different Sources

Figure 3: Axon 3 in three conditions.